

MOSAIC STYLE IN MODERN FINE ART

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Annotation: This article describes the mosaic style in modern fine art, the colors and materials used in modern mosaic fine art.

Key words: modern fine art, mosaic style, pictorial elements, combination.

Introduction:

In modern fine art, the mosaic style is a style created by combining small pieces of different materials. Mosaic - patterns and pictures created by cutting and arranging stone, glass, ceramic, metal or other materials in different colors. This method has been used in various cultures throughout history, but it was especially common during the Roman Empire.

Literature analysis and methodology:

In modern times, mosaic art has been accepted as a traditional art form, but it has also become a form of expression used by contemporary artists. Mosaic can be applied to walls, paintings, sculptures and other surfaces and can use different colors, patterns and textures to create visual impact.

Mosaic gives an opportunity to express the artist's creativity as well as visual expression. Assembling pieces requires the artist to consider elements such as composition, color harmony, and use of texture. The different surfaces of the materials used in the mosaic change the reflection of light and shadows, which brings depth and vitality to the work.

Contemporary artists can combine traditional mosaic techniques with modern concepts and themes to create innovative works. Mixed media works combining mosaic with other mediums may also appear. Although mosaic is a time-tested art form, it is still used today as a modern and creative form of expression. With mosaics, artists can explore different styles and aesthetics and create their own unique pieces.

The mosaic style in modern fine art is a modern interpretation of mosaic art. Mosaic means combining small colored pieces to create a pattern or picture. Over time, the art of mosaics also evolved and began to be used in different styles and styles.

Results:

In modern Taniy art, the mosaic style creates a modern and contemporary aesthetic using traditional mosaic techniques. This approach allows you to create realistic pictures, as well as abstract or symbolic expressions. Mosaic can be used to create patterns and compositions by combining different materials.

In modern fine art, the mosaic style is a style of creating images using mosaic materials in particular. Mosaic is used in the creation of external faces, consisting of many colored material sleeves. These parts are combined either unchanged or correctly located on the main viewing surface.

The mosaic style is very popular in modern art, mainly developed in the early 20th century by the Italian artist Severini and the Russian artist Larionov. The sweetest and most necessary learning process for them has become very important. The main feature of this style is to allow all the sleeves to be assembled flat and endlessly with each other.

Discussion:

Mosaic style, images and panels, used in mosaic panels and wholes placed on stone. Images in this style are created by applying colors directly or often late. Graphical elements are integrated with other mosaic segments on the base or panel on which they are located.

The style of mosaic is one of the most important activities in modern visual art, and the combination of different techniques, methods, and materials revolves around mosaic. Through this method, people have been able to use the most important images and the characteristics of life.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that there are many colors and materials used in modern mosaic art. In this style, files are created from grass, glass, stone and other special materials. Mosaic is used in a wide range of images, buildings, hotels, physical regulatory indicators, etc. Where they can be seen, the visual works created through the mosaic style will not be difficult to manage.

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